

STUDIES ON THE CIRCULAR DICHROISM AND ROTATORY DISPERSION.
PART IV. MEASUREMENT OF ABSORPTION, CIRCULAR
DICHROISM AND ROTATORY DISPERSION OF
SODIUM VANADYL *d*-TARTRATE

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Measurement of absorption, circular dichroism and the rotatory dispersion of sodium vanadyl *d*-tartrate have been carried out. The absorption bands and the circular dichroism and rotatory dispersion associated with the absorption bands have been represented by the empirical equation published by the author in a previous paper (Kar, this *Journal*, 1947, 24, 461)

Studies on the circular dichroism and rotatory dispersion of ammonium vanadyl *d*-tartrate and potassium vanadyl *d*-tartrate have already been made in this laboratory (Kar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 22, 278; 1947, 25, 117; 1948, 25, 267). In the present communication the investigation has been extended to sodium vanadyl *d*-tartrate.

EXPERIMENTAL

Sodium vanadyl *d*-tartrate was prepared in the same way as the ammonium salt and potassium salt (Kar, *loc. cit.*). In place of ammonium vanadate, sodium vanadate was taken.

Measurements of absorption, rotation and ellipticity were carried out by the same method and apparatus as described in previous parts and similar results have been obtained.

Analysis of the Absorption Curves.—The extinction coefficients have been calculated by the equation

$$\epsilon = \frac{2 \log \tan \theta}{l}$$

where θ is the spectrophotometric reading and l is the length in cm. and have been tabulated in Table I and are represented graphically in Fig. 1. The molecular extinction coefficient has not been calculated, as the water of crystallisation of the molecule of sodium vanadyl *d*-tartrate is not known to us. The first absorption band is reduced to a 'step out' the maximum of which is very difficult to ascertain, while the second absorption band shows a maximum at about 5172 Å. Attempts have been made to analyse the second absorption band only. The following equations have been used to analyse the second absorption curve.

(a) Equation of Ketteler and Helmholtz

$$\epsilon = \frac{a\lambda^2}{(\lambda^2 - \lambda_m^2)^2 + g^2\lambda^2}$$

where ϵ = extinction coefficient at wave-length, λ ; λ_m = the wave-length corresponding to the head of the band; a and g^2 are constants.

- (b) Equation of Bielecki and Henri (*Physikal. Z.*, 1913, **14**, 516).
 (c) Equation of Kuhn (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1929, **4**, 14; *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1930, **26**, 293).
 (d) Equation of Kuhn and Braun (*ibid.*, 1930, **8**, 281).
 (e) Equation of Lowry and Hudson (*Phil. Trans.*, 1933, **A**, 232, 117).
 (f) Equation of Kar (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1947, **24**, 461).

The extinction coefficients calculated from those six equations are tabulated in Table I. It is interesting to note that our equation represents the experimental data better than any other equations.

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

Analysis of the Curves of Circular Dichroism.—Measurement of ellipticity was carried out in both the absorption bands and these are found to be opposite in sign. From the ellipticity, the circular dichroism has been calculated by the relation

$$(\epsilon_1 - \epsilon_2) = \frac{4 \times 0.4343 \times \phi}{57.296 \times l}$$

where ϕ is the ellipticity expressed in degrees and l is the length of the solution in centimetre. The observed values of $(\epsilon_1 - \epsilon_2)$ are given in Table II against the respective frequencies. The experimental curve of circular dichroism for both the bands is represented in Fig. 2. The dissymmetry factor $g = (\epsilon_1 - \epsilon_2)/\epsilon$ is also tabulated in Table II. The circular dichroism curves have been represented by our empirical equations (*loc. cit.*) and the calculated values of $(\epsilon_1 - \epsilon_2)$ are given in Table II.

Analysis of the Curve of Rotatory Dispersion.—The experimental data for the measurement of the rotatory dispersion are given in Table III. These observed rotations $[\alpha]$ for each wave-length are the algebraic sum of all the partial rotations due to different optically active absorption bands in the visible and ultraviolet regions. These observed values of rotations are represented graphically as curve 1 in Fig. 3.

The following equations have been used to analyse the curve of rotatory dispersion :

- (a) Equation of Kuhn and Braun (*loc. cit.*) in the form as used by the author

FIG. 3

Rotatory dispersion of sodium vanadyl *d*-tartrate.

1. Experimental curve.
2. Theoretical curve calculated from the equation of Kuhn and Braun.
3. Theoretical curve calculated from the equation of Lowry and Hudson.
4. - - - - Theoretical curve calculated from our equation.
5. Difference curve (curve 1 minus curve 2).
6. Difference curve (curve 1 minus curve 3).
7. - - - - Difference curve (curve 1 minus curve 4).

(*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1947, **24**, 461). The values of $(\epsilon_1 - \epsilon_2)_{\max}$, ν_0 and θ for both the curves of circular dichroism are already given in Table II. The rotatory contributions at different wave-lengths for each of the absorption bands have been calculated separately. The algebraic sum of the calculated partial rotations $[\alpha]_1$ and $[\alpha]_2$ for different wave-lengths of the two optically active absorption bands in the visible region and the difference between $[\alpha]$ and $[\alpha]_1 + [\alpha]_2$ are given in Table III. This difference evidently represents the residual rotations due to absorption bands in the ultraviolet region. The algebraic sum of the calculated partial rotations and also the residual rotation are represented graphically as curves 2 and 5 in Fig. 3. The difference curve 5 should be normal, *i.e.*, the rotation should increase progressively with decreasing wave-lengths in the region of the first and second absorption bands but

TABLE IA

 $c = 3 \text{ g./100 c. c. } l = 5 \text{ mm. } t = 30^\circ.$

First absorption band

$\nu \times 10^{-14}$	4.285	4.379	4.470	4.659	4.771	4.839	4.916	4.999	5.091
ϵ obs.	0.753	0.830	0.892	1.004	1.046	1.061	1.097	1.142	1.217

TABLE IB

Equation of Ketteler and Helmholtz : $a = 1.3 \times 10^4$; $g^2 = 7.94 \times 10^5$; $\lambda_m = 5172 \text{ \AA.}$ Equation of Bielecki and Henri : $a = 2.83 \times 10^{-1}$; $g = 2.88 \times 10^{-4}$; $\nu_0 = 580.$ Equation of Kuhn : $\epsilon_{\max} = 1.64$; $\nu' \times 10^{-14} = 1.60$; $\nu_0 \times 10^{-14} = 5.8.$ Equation of Kuhn and Braun and of Lowry and Hudson : $\epsilon_{\max} = 1.64$; $\nu_0 \times 10^{-14} = 5.8$; $\theta \times 10^{-14} = 0.9705.$ Kar's equation : $\epsilon_{\max} = 1.64$; $\nu_0 \times 10^{-14} = 5.8$; $\nu_1 \times 10^{-14} = 4.72$; $\theta_1 \times 10^{14} = 1.297$; $\nu_2 \times 10^{-14} = 6.32$; $\theta_2 \times 10^{-14} = 0.6246.$

Second absorption band

$\nu \times 10^{-14}$	$\epsilon_{\text{obs.}}$	$\epsilon_{\text{calc.}}$ (K & H)	$\epsilon_{\text{calc.}}$ (B & H)	$\epsilon_{\text{calc.}}$ (Kuhn)	$\epsilon_{\text{calc.}}$ (K & B)	$\epsilon_{\text{calc.}}$ (L & H)	$\epsilon_{\text{calc.}}$ (Kar)
5.193	1.278	0.613	0.508	1.041	1.109	1.007	1.317
5.266	1.349	0.719	0.655	1.570	1.212	1.135	1.385
5.357	1.389	0.884	0.847	1.196	1.331	1.275	1.460
5.493	1.522	1.170	1.183	1.425	1.484	1.467	1.551
5.607	1.548	1.418	1.424	1.550	1.576	1.571	1.604
5.759	1.636	1.626	1.621	1.636	1.637	1.637	1.638
5.820	1.610	1.634	1.644	1.639	1.639	1.639	1.639
5.898	1.488	1.577	1.622	1.615	1.623	1.624	1.600
6.122	1.186	1.175	1.284	1.411	1.469	1.486	1.257
6.25	0.892	0.934	0.986	1.246	1.322	1.362	0.976
6.353	0.750	0.772	0.745	1.11	1.185	1.251	0.749
6.413	0.704	0.693	0.614	1.033	1.10	1.183	0.626

it contains loops. These loops may be attributed partly to experimental errors and partly to the fact that the above equation cannot represent the experimental data accurately.

(b) Equation of Lowry and Hudson ("Optical Rotatory Power", Cambridge, 1935, p. 449) in the form as used by the author in Part III of this series (*loc. cit.*).

$$\alpha = \frac{57.3}{2\sqrt{\pi}} \frac{(\epsilon_1 - \epsilon_2)_{\max}}{\log_{10} e} \frac{\nu}{\nu_0} \left[e^{-\left[\frac{\nu_0}{\nu} \left(\frac{\nu_0 - \nu}{\theta} \right) \right]^2} \int_0^{\frac{\nu_0}{\nu} \left(\frac{\nu_0 - \nu}{\theta} \right)} e^{x^2} dx + \frac{\nu\theta}{2\nu_0(\nu_0 + \nu)} \right]$$

TABLE II

Conc. of sodium vanadyl *d*-tartrate = 3 g./100 c. c.
l = 1 cm. *t* = 30°.

First curve of circular dichroism				Second curve of circular dichroism			
$\nu_0 \times 10^{-14} = 4.711$; $(\epsilon_l - \epsilon_r)_{\max.} = 0.064$; $\nu_1 \times 10^{-14} = 4.37$; $\theta_1 \times 10^{-14} = 0.4805$; $\nu_2 \times 10^{-14} = 4.08$; $\theta_2 \times 10^{-14} = 0.3243$; $\theta \times 10^{-14} = 0.4024$.				$\nu_0 \times 10^{-14} = 5.78$; $(\epsilon_l - \epsilon_r)_{\max.} = 0.1156$; $\nu_1 \times 10^{-14} = 5.41$; $\theta_1 \times 10^{-14} = 0.4444$; $\nu_2 \times 10^{-14} = 6.36$; $\theta_2 \times 10^{-14} = 0.6966$; $\theta \times 10^{-14} = 0.5706$.			
$\nu \times 10^{-14}$.	$(\epsilon_l - \epsilon_r)_{\text{obs.}}$	$(\epsilon_l - \epsilon_r)_{\text{calc.}}$	<i>g.</i>	$\nu \times 10^{-14}$.	$(\epsilon_l - \epsilon_r)_{\text{obs.}}$	$(\epsilon_l - \epsilon_r)_{\text{calc.}}$	<i>g.</i>
4.285	-0.0288	-0.02916	-0.0382	5.193	0.0112	0.0202	0.0088
4.379	-0.04	-0.0397	-0.0482	5.266	0.0327	0.0303	0.0243
4.470	-0.0491	-0.0498	-0.0551	5.493	0.0776	0.0641	0.051
4.659	-0.0606	-0.0633	-0.0604	5.607	0.0982	0.0993	0.0634
4.711	-0.0643	...	-0.06144	5.759	0.1152	0.1153	0.0704
4.839	-0.0521	-0.0548	-0.0491	5.82	0.1110	0.1154	0.069
4.916	-0.0449	-0.0429	-0.0409	5.898	0.1061	0.1123	0.0713
4.999	-0.0339	-0.0291	-0.0297	6.250	0.0685	0.0733	0.0769
5.091	-0.0109	-0.0162	-0.0090	6.413	0.0555	0.0506	0.0788

The algebraic sum of the calculated partial rotation $[\alpha]_1$ and $[\alpha]_2$ and the difference between the observed rotations and this algebraic sum are tabulated in Table III. The algebraic sum of the calculated partial rotations and also the difference are also represented graphically as curves 3 and 6 in Fig. 3. The difference curve 6 shows no sign of improvement towards disappearance of the loops, thus indicating that the equation of Lowry and Hudson is also inadequate to represent the experimental data accurately.

TABLE III

Conc. of sodium vanadyl *d*-tartrate = 3 g./100 c. c. *l* = 1 cm. *t* = 30°.
 Observed rotation $[\alpha] = X$. Algebraic sum of the calculated partial rotations according to different equations, $[\alpha]_1 + [\alpha]_2 = Y$.

λ .	X.	Kuhn & Braun		Lowry & Hudson		Y.	Kar	X - Y.
		Y.	X - Y.	Y.	X - Y.			
7000 Å	0.95	-0.51	1.46	-0.64	1.59	-0.71		1.66
6850	1.41	-0.48	1.89	-0.66	2.07	-0.60		2.01
6708	1.43	-0.28	1.71	-0.48	1.91	-0.37		1.80
6438	2.21	0.73	1.48	0.53	1.68	0.49		1.72
6362	2.30	1.11	1.19	0.90	1.40	0.81		1.49
6000	4.20	2.98	1.22	2.78	1.42	2.67		1.53
5893	4.20	3.26	0.94	3.17	1.03	2.86		1.34
5700	4.26	3.30	0.96	3.48	0.78	3.00		1.26
5350	3.20	1.84	1.36	2.13	1.07	2.02		1.18
5209	1.86	0.93	0.93	1.02	0.84	0.62		1.24
5086	0.86	-0.39	1.25	-0.10	0.96	-0.41		1.27
4800	0.30	-2.12	2.42	-1.80	2.10	-2.08		2.38
4678	0.25	-2.18	2.43	-1.97	2.22	-2.26		2.51

(c) Equation of Kar (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1947, **24**, 461). The algebraic sum of the calculated partial rotations and the difference between the observed rotation and this sum are also given in Table III and represented graphically as curves 4 and 7 in Fig. 3. The difference curve 7 shows that the loop, which has to be eliminated, shows a sign of improvement, though not disappeared, thus indicating that our equation represents the partial rotations of both the bands more accurately than the equation of Kuhn and Braun and^d of Lowry and Hudson.

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